

The use of Spatial Data Analysis (SDA) techniques for the elaboration of quantitative landslide susceptibility models

Remondo, J., Bonachea, J., Díaz de Terán, J.R., González-Díez, A., Cendrero, A., Chung, C.J. and Fabbri, A.

INTRODUCTION

Mass movements are an important geomorphological process as well as a potential threat for human lives and property; it is thus important to design and implement measures to mitigate the hazard they represent. An important tool for the design of mitigation strategies and plans are susceptibility, hazard or risk maps. However, the elaboration of such maps is not a simple task, due to the complexity of these phenomena and the difficulty to properly assess their future behaviour.

The extent of areas to be analysed for regional hazard mapping makes the application of deterministic models un-viable. The solution to this problem can be better approached through the use of probabilistic models. Spatial Data Analysis (SDA) methods developed during the last decade offer the possibility to apply probabilistic models that enable a satisfactory determination of potential instability.

Slope instability or landslide susceptibility maps thus obtained are the basis for subsequent hazard maps. The methodology here illustrated has been applied in the Bajo Deva valley, northern Spain (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Location map of the study area.

DATA USED

- Spatial database including landslide causal factors (15 thematic layers are used).
- Spatial data sets of past instability signs (pre-1954, 1954-71, 1971-83, 1983-85, 1985-91, 1991-93, 1993-97). This is a crucial input for the whole analysis.

DATA PRE-PROCESSING

If the analysis is performed using pre-existing databases, adaptation of these, error-filtering, etc. must be carried out beforehand. This is an important time-consuming step. A series of thematic layers representing a variety of landform characteristics are derived from DEM. Dependency relationships between thematic layers should be analysed to avoid double counting. Continuous variables were categorised.

OPERATING STEPS (Figure 2)

- Creation of unique condition sub-areas by overlay of all thematic layers.
- Estimation of favourability values by means of bivariate relationships between map of past movements and individual thematic layers.
- Integration of favourability values applying a specific favourability function.
- Re-classification of study area into 200 susceptibility classes (each one with 0.5% of the final values).

VALIDATION

The susceptibility maps obtained represent a hypothesis that must be validated. Validation has been made by splitting past movements into several time groups "older for analysis" and "younger for control" (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Validation curves of landslide susceptibility model elaborated on the basis of 1954-1983 movements using slope gradient, elevation, aspect, lithology and vegetation as variables. Validation was carried out with landslides occurred during 1983-85, 1983-91 and 1983-97.

The temporal analysis is the basis for the elaboration of probabilistic hazard models. Maps showing the spatial-temporal probability of occurrence of future landslides have been thus obtained (Figure 4). The observed trends of change in landslide frequency enable to develop more realistic scenarios for future behaviour of slopes than those based just in past frequency (Figures 5 and 6, and Table 1). In this way, the analysis of the geomorphological evolution has made possible the incorporation of such scenarios in the hazard models, that increase their prediction capability.

Figure 5. Observed landslide frequency in each susceptibility class and best fit (see Table 1)

Figure 6. Extrapolation of future landslide frequency for the three scenarios (see Table 1).
 A) Total No. Of landslides in next 50 years equal to past 50 years.
 B) No. Of landslides per year in the future equivalent to last 5 years.
 C) No. Of landslides increasing yearly according to past trend.

Susceptibility class	% de la zona	Eventos totales	Prob. A (50 años)	Prob. B (50 años)	Prob. C (50 años)
200	0	0	0	0	0
199	0.1	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001	0.0001
198	0.2	0.0002	0.0002	0.0002	0.0002
197	0.3	0.0003	0.0003	0.0003	0.0003
196	0.4	0.0004	0.0004	0.0004	0.0004
195	0.5	0.0005	0.0005	0.0005	0.0005
194	0.6	0.0006	0.0006	0.0006	0.0006
193	0.7	0.0007	0.0007	0.0007	0.0007
192	0.8	0.0008	0.0008	0.0008	0.0008
191	0.9	0.0009	0.0009	0.0009	0.0009
190	1.0	0.0010	0.0010	0.0010	0.0010
189	1.1	0.0011	0.0011	0.0011	0.0011
188	1.2	0.0012	0.0012	0.0012	0.0012
187	1.3	0.0013	0.0013	0.0013	0.0013
186	1.4	0.0014	0.0014	0.0014	0.0014
185	1.5	0.0015	0.0015	0.0015	0.0015
184	1.6	0.0016	0.0016	0.0016	0.0016
183	1.7	0.0017	0.0017	0.0017	0.0017
182	1.8	0.0018	0.0018	0.0018	0.0018
181	1.9	0.0019	0.0019	0.0019	0.0019
180	2.0	0.0020	0.0020	0.0020	0.0020
179	2.1	0.0021	0.0021	0.0021	0.0021
178	2.2	0.0022	0.0022	0.0022	0.0022
177	2.3	0.0023	0.0023	0.0023	0.0023
176	2.4	0.0024	0.0024	0.0024	0.0024
175	2.5	0.0025	0.0025	0.0025	0.0025
174	2.6	0.0026	0.0026	0.0026	0.0026
173	2.7	0.0027	0.0027	0.0027	0.0027
172	2.8	0.0028	0.0028	0.0028	0.0028
171	2.9	0.0029	0.0029	0.0029	0.0029
170	3.0	0.0030	0.0030	0.0030	0.0030
169	3.1	0.0031	0.0031	0.0031	0.0031
168	3.2	0.0032	0.0032	0.0032	0.0032
167	3.3	0.0033	0.0033	0.0033	0.0033
166	3.4	0.0034	0.0034	0.0034	0.0034
165	3.5	0.0035	0.0035	0.0035	0.0035
164	3.6	0.0036	0.0036	0.0036	0.0036
163	3.7	0.0037	0.0037	0.0037	0.0037
162	3.8	0.0038	0.0038	0.0038	0.0038
161	3.9	0.0039	0.0039	0.0039	0.0039
160	4.0	0.0040	0.0040	0.0040	0.0040
159	4.1	0.0041	0.0041	0.0041	0.0041
158	4.2	0.0042	0.0042	0.0042	0.0042
157	4.3	0.0043	0.0043	0.0043	0.0043
156	4.4	0.0044	0.0044	0.0044	0.0044
155	4.5	0.0045	0.0045	0.0045	0.0045
154	4.6	0.0046	0.0046	0.0046	0.0046
153	4.7	0.0047	0.0047	0.0047	0.0047
152	4.8	0.0048	0.0048	0.0048	0.0048
151	4.9	0.0049	0.0049	0.0049	0.0049
150	5.0	0.0050	0.0050	0.0050	0.0050

Table 1. Landslide susceptibility, frequency and hazard Extrapolations of landslide probability for three scenarios are presented (see Figures 5 and 6).

Figure 4. Landslide hazard map for the Deva study area, expressed as probability of occurrence (for each pixel) during the next 45 years (scenario A, Figure 6)

CONCLUSIONS

The method proposed provides satisfactory landslide susceptibility maps. This maps can then be used to elaborate hazard maps, expressed in terms of spatial-temporal probability.

Results presented show that forecasts of future natural hazards should incorporate not only climate change but also economic and land use change scenarios. The latter control to a great extent terrain sensitivity to triggering factors, and therefore spatial and temporal probability of future events.

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Susceptibility class	% de la zona	Frecuencia	Frec. A (50 años)	Frec. B (50 años)	Frec. C (50 años)
1	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
2	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
3	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
4	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
5	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
6	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
7	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
8	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
9	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
10	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
11	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
12	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
13	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
14	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
15	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
16	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
17	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
18	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
19	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
20	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
21	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
22	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
23	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
24	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
25	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
26	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
27	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
28	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
29	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
30	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
31	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
32	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
33	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
34	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
35	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
36	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
37	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
38	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
39	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
40	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
41	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
42	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
43	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
44	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
45	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
46	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
47	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
48	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
49	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
50	0.1	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000

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